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Correction: Viscoelastic interfaces comprising of cellulose nanocrystals and lauroyl ethyl arginate for enhanced foam stability

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Correction for 'Viscoelastic interfaces comprising of cellulose nanocrystals and lauroyl ethyl arginate for enhanced foam stability' by Agnieszka Czakaj *et al.*, *Soft Matter*, 2020, **16**, 3981–3990, DOI: 10.1039/C9SM02392E.

The authors would like to correct Fig. 8. Due to the original colours used, not all of the lines on the graph were visible. The corrected version of Fig. 8 is shown below.

Fig. 8 Time evolution of the dynamic surface tension as a function of LAE concentration without and with the presence of 0.3 wt% CNC.

The Royal Society of Chemistry apologises for these errors and any consequent inconvenience to authors and readers.

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